

EFFECT OF ACCESS TO FINANCIAL SERVICES ON THE WELFARE OF MEMBERS OF WOMEN COOPERATIVE SOCIETIES IN ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract

Increasing women's access to financial services is important because financial inclusion is generally considered a key enabler of economic growth and poverty reduction. This study is on effect of access to financial services on the welfare of members of women cooperative societies in Anambra state, Nigeria. It specifically, determined the effect of access to financial services on the welfare of members of women cooperative societies in Anambra state. It adopted a descriptive survey research design that aimed at determining the relationship between the independent variable and dependent variable in a population. The population of this study was made up of 2997 members of women cooperative societies in Anambra state. A sample of 341 was determined for the study using Krejcie & Morgan table for determining sample size of a known population. A structured questionnaire was administered to 341 respondents and analysis was done based on the 297 duly completed and returned questionnaire. The data collected using the questionnaire were analysed using descriptive statistics like frequency, mean and standard deviation; and also inferential statistics such as regression analysis and Z-test statistics. All analyses were conducted using E-View version 7. Findings show that access to financial services has a significant positive effect on the welfare of members of women cooperative societies. The study recommends that seminars and workshops be organized for educating women on various programmes designed to enhance access to finance. The study has contributed to knowledge by narrowing the implications of financial inclusion on welfare of members of women cooperative in Anambra state.

Keywords: Financial Services, Welfare, Women Cooperative Societies, Anambra State.

Introduction

Background of the Study

Financial inclusion enables individuals to have access to financial services; thereby enabling them invest so that they generate income and hence increase their income. The increase in income is one of the panaceas for poverty reduction. Having access to financial services allows firms to invest and households to smooth their consumption and build capital over time, which leads to improvement in the business environment as well as people's livelihoods. Increasing access to and use of quality financial products

and services is essential to inclusive economic growth and poverty reduction. Research shows that when people participate in the financial system, they are better able to manage risk, start or invest in a business, and fund large expenditures like education or a home improvement (Ashraf, Karlan and Yin, 2010; Dupas and Robinson, 2013; Cull, Robert, Tilman and Nina 2014; Ugwa, et. al. 2015).

Increasing women's access to financial services is important because financial inclusion is generally considered a key enabler of economic growth and poverty reduction; it is seen as a driver of economic development. Financial services help people to escape poverty by facilitating investments in their health, education and businesses. Mehrotra, Puhazhendhi, Nair and Sahoo (2009) emphasize that access to financial services allows the poor to save money outside the house safety and helps in mitigating the risks that the poor faces as a result of economic shocks. Providing women with effective and affordable financial tools to save and borrow money, make and receive payments, and manage risk is critical to both women's empowerment and poverty reduction.

The study is necessitated by perceived exclusion of women particularly in rural areas from financial services, which includes having access to financial services. In terms of access to financial services, a number of indicators like dependence on the husbands, cultural restrictions, lack of income, lack of exposure, lack/ low of education, and low trust serve as impediments for women to have access to Financial Service Providers (FSPs).

Presently, the government, financial institutions and other agencies have made concerted efforts in addressing the problem of lack of access to financial services received by women in Nigeria and Anambra State in particular. Women are encouraged to form themselves into cooperatives to enable them access various empowerment packages and have more access to financial services. However, it is not yet certain the extent to which these efforts have yielded the desired result thus warranting an empirical investigation into this study area, hence the need for this study.

Research Question

- ✓ “ To what extent does access to financial services affect services on the welfare of members of women cooperative societies in Anambra state, Nigeria?

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study is to

- ✓ Determine the effect of access to financial services on the welfare of members of women cooperative societies in Anambra state, Nigeria.

Hypothesis of the Study

- ✓ H₀₁: Access to financial services has no significant effect on the welfare of members of women cooperative societies in Anambra state.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The Concept of Financial Inclusion

Financial inclusion means that individuals and businesses have access to useful and affordable financial products and services that meet their needs – transactions, payments, savings, credit and insurance – delivered in a responsible and sustainable way.

Financial inclusion has been defined in many different ways by various authors. In early academic papers, financial inclusion is defined indirectly in terms of exclusion, and was related to the broader context of social exclusion.

Demirguc-Kunt and Klapper, (2012) define financial inclusion simply as the number of adults that have an individual and/or joint account at a formal financial institution. Financial inclusion refers to the timely delivery of financial services to the disadvantaged and low income group at an affordable cost (Serrao, Sequeira, and Varambally 2013). It includes availability of, and access to different types of formal financial services at reasonable price. Financial inclusion is the benchmark used to assess how formal financial services reach the common people in the economy (Uma, Rupa, and Madhu (2013). It is a term commonly used to represent the deliberate attempt which makes the poor, marginalised people and those vulnerable to low economic power to engage in formal economic process through ownership and usage of formal financial service at regular interval. Financial inclusion is the enabling access to financial resources and service for different economic agents at an affordable cost, especially to those with lower income (Mbutor and Uba, 2013).

Demirguc-Kunt and Klapper, (2012) define financial inclusion simply as the number of adults that have an individual and/or joint account at a formal financial institution.

The ability of the poor to access easy, affordable and safe financial services is a pre-condition for accelerating inclusive growth (Serrao *et al.* 2013; Okonkwo, et. al. 2017; Otaokpukpu, et. al. 2017) because poverty is usually synonymous with financial exclusion whereby people are directly and indirectly excluded from formal financial system. As a result of this financial exclusion, people are left with the option of patronising the informal finance providers which in most cases are expensive, not organised and full of doubts. However, access to banking services will empower the poor by giving them opportunity to have a bank account, to save and invest which help to lift them out of poverty (Nalini and Mariappan, 2012).

The first step towards financial inclusion is having access to a transaction account. Transaction account allows people to store money, send and receive payments. A transaction account serves as a gateway to other financial services. Financial access facilitates day-to-day living and helps families and businesses plan for everything from long term goals to unexpected emergencies. As account holders, people are more likely to use other financial services such as credit and insurance.

Indicators for Measuring Financial Inclusion

The main types of indicators to consider when measuring financial inclusion are:

- **Access indicators** reflect the depth of outreach of financial services, such as the penetration of bank branches or point of sale (POS) devices in rural areas, or demand-side barriers that customers face to access financial institutions, such as cost or information.
- **Usage indicators** measure how clients use financial services, such as the regularity and duration of the financial product/service over time (e.g. average savings balances, number of transactions per account, number of electronic payments made).
- **Quality** measures describe whether financial products and services match clients' needs, the range of options available to customers, and clients' awareness and understanding of financial products. (Nalini and Mariappan, 2012; Okonkwo and Ugwa, 2020; Okonkwo, et. al. 2018).

Access to Financial Inclusion

Access to financial inclusion is the ability to use available financial services from formal finance providers which depends on the conditions for the opening and using a bank account (Serrao *et al.* 2013) such as location of banks to the people and the charges paid to the bank for operating a bank account. The findings of Uma *at al.* (2013) provide a clear support for the above as they found that it took two weeks for 87% of their respondents for their accounts to function after the submission of the completed bank account opening application forms. 80% visited their banks just once in a month while 50% keep their money at home rather than the bank.

Access to formal financial services or financial inclusion in developing economies is critical to economic growth and reduction in inequality among citizens of a nation. Financial power that is derived where access to finance is possible could create a partition between the rich and the poor, educated and illiterate, and urban and rural dwellers because those with formal financial access have unlimited access to enhance their financial power with varied options from the formal finance providers. Serrao *et al.* (2013) assert that the lack of access to finance is a critical mechanism for the persistent income inequality, as well as slower growth which influences resource allocation and the comparative economic opportunities of individuals of the economy.

Access to formal finance creates opportunity for people to increase their income and productivity through purchase and sales of goods and services with possibility of reduction in poverty and improvement in standard of living.

Empirical Review

Evans and Adeoye (2016) investigated the contributing determinants of financial inclusion in Africa spanning 2005 to 2014. Historical data for 15 African countries were collated from the World Development Index for the analyses and estimation using

dynamic panel regression technique. The study adopted number of depositors with commercial banks per 1,000 adults as the dependent variable and gross domestic product per capita, broad money supply (M2) to GDP, the ratio of credit to the real sector to GDP, inflation, number of people with internet access, internet servers, adult literacy rate, population, savings rate and a dummy for Islamic banking as explanatory variables of the study. The results indicate that GDP capita income, broad money to GDP, level of literacy, access to internet and dummy of Islamic banking are key determinants of financial inclusion. It also emerged that the proportion of credit to the real sector to GDP, savings rates, inflation and population are inconsequential determinants of financial inclusion in Africa.

David, Oluseyi and Emmanuel (2018) examined the determinants of financial inclusion in Nigeria. Time series data spanning 1990 to 2016 were collated and estimated using error correction technique. The dependent variable is the number of depositors with deposit money banks per 1,000 adults, while the independent variables are gross domestic product per capita, the ratio of broad money supply to gross domestic product, credit to micro, small and medium enterprises and internet users. The study found that gross domestic product per capita, the ratio of broad money supply to gross domestic product, credit to micro, small and medium enterprises and internet users are significant determinants of financial inclusion in Nigeria.

Efobi, Beecroft and Osabuohien (2014) investigated the use and access to bank financial services in Nigeria. The objective of the paper was to ascertain key indicators of inclusive bank finance in Nigeria. Historical data were collated from the World Bank Findex data repository of 2011. The dependent metrics of the study are the usage of banking financial services, account usage – savings and withdrawals. The independent metrics used are age, income, penchant for IT use, gender, education and financial discipline. A probit model was built and estimated using multiple regressions. The results indicate that the major determinants of inclusive finance are age, income and individuals with the penchant for IT use. Other variables were found to be insignificant.

Amendola, Boccia, Mele and Sensini (2016) investigated the relationship between financial access and household welfare in Mauritania. The study used micro-level data from a 2014 household survey and the ordinary least squares technique is employed as the analytical tool. The result shows that household headed by the aged, educated people and residents in urban areas is associated with better access to financial services which in turn improves welfare.

Nanziri (2016) examined the relationship between financial inclusion and welfare in South Africa. The study uses the ordinary least square estimation technique. The results indicate that better financial inclusion is associated with higher welfare. The author further indicates that women who use non-formal credit have lower welfare.

Tita and Aziakpono (2017) examined the nexus between financial inclusion and welfare in sub-saharan Africa by using disaggregated data for the analysis. The result shows that formal accounted use for business, electronic payment and formal savings have a positive relationship with welfare.

Mallick and Zhang (2019) estimated the effects of financial inclusion on household welfare in China. The study shows that the effects of financial inclusion on welfare varied across urban and rural areas and income groups. It is further revealed that financial inclusion significantly increases overall consumption, but the impact is greater for urban households compared with rural household.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. It covered the women cooperative societies in the 21 Local Government Areas in Anambra. The population of the study is made up of members of all women cooperative societies. There were 312 women cooperative societies in Anambra with a total membership of 2997 in the 21 Local Government Area of the state. A multi stage random sampling technique was adopted in selecting the 341 members that formed the population for the study. Data was gotten from both primary and secondary sources. The main instrument for the collection of primary data was a structured questionnaire constructed solely for the purpose of the study while that of secondary data is textbook.

Method of Data Analysis

Data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, mean, and standard deviation) and the inferential statistics (Simple Linear Regression). The objective of the study was processed using descriptive statistics (like percentages, mean and standard deviation) and the regression model of the Ordinary Least Square (OLS). Z-test and F-test statistics were used to test the hypothesis of the study.

All the analyses were done using E-View version 7. Linear regression model of the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) approach was used to analyse the objectives in order to ascertain the influence and also determine the relationship between the independent variables and dependent variable in the conceptualized model of the study. The use of Ordinary Least Square (OLS) is informed by the fact that under normality assumption for α_i , the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) estimator is normally distributed and is said to be best, unbiased linear estimator (Gujarati & Porter, 2008).

Determine the effect of access to financial services on the welfare of members of women cooperative societies in Anambra state, Nigeria.

To determine the effect of access to financial services on the welfare of members of women cooperative societies in Anambra state and the hypothesis put forward for testing is that access to financial services has no significant effect on the welfare of members of women cooperative societies in Anambra state.

Data was collected using structured questionnaire, with 10 items, 5 each was used to measure the dependent variable (welfare of members of women cooperative societies) and independent variable (access to financial services).

Table 1: Distribution of responses on access to Financial Services and Welfare of Members of Women Cooperative Societies

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	UD	D	SD	Mean
Access to Finance							
1	I own a bank account that gives me access to funds.	111	126	-	39	21	3.90
2	I have assets that I can easily convert to cash	76	68	32	73	66	3.17
3	I frequently use mobile money to get funds.	54	91	-	90	62	2.95
4	Credit facilities are easily accessed by me.	36	99	-	72	90	2.73
5	I have options to get finance.	17	90	3	105	82	2.51
Welfare of Members							
6	I can buy what I want if I have greater access to capital.	105	115	21	24	32	3.80
7	My standard of living will improve if I can get credit facilities.	153	90	13	41	-	4.20
8	Better health care will be assured with improve access to funds.	115	149	15	18	-	4.11
9	My life will be better if I can get enough money to carry out my business.	92	171	9	19	6	4.09
10	I will love it more if I have options to access finance.	198	99	-	-	-	4.67

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 1 shows the distribution of responses for questionnaire items measuring Access to Financial Services and Welfare of Members of Women Cooperative Societies in Anambra state. The analysis here is based on the mean of the individual questionnaire items, with an acceptance threshold of 3 and above and a rejection benchmark of below 3 cumulatively.

Starting from the questionnaire items bothering on access to financial services, the respondents accepted that they own bank accounts that give them access to funds with a mean of 3.90 which is greater than the acceptance threshold of 3. Similarly, they also concurred that they have assets that they can easily convert to cash as shown with a mean of 3.17 (greater than the benchmark of 3). The respondents however rejected that

they frequently use mobile money to get funds as shown by a mean of 2.95 which is less than the benchmark of 3. A mean of 2.73 also shows that they rejected that credit facilities are easily accessed by them. This was also followed by the rejection of the insinuation that they have options to get finance was shown by a mean of 2.51.

For questionnaire items used in capturing Welfare of Members of Women Cooperative Societies in Anambra state as related to access to finance, the respondents accepted that they can buy what they want if they have greater access to capital as shown with a mean 3.80 which is greater than the threshold of 3. They also accepted that their standard of living will improve if they can get credit facilities with a mean of 4.20. In the same line of thought, they also accepted that better health care will be assured with improve access to funds with a mean of 4.11. A mean of 4.09 and 4.67 show that the respondents concurred that their life will be better if they can get enough money to carry out their business and that they will love it more if they have options to access finance respectively.

Hypothesis One

Ho₁: Access to financial services has no significant effect on the welfare of members of women cooperative societies in Anambra state.

Table 2: Regression Analysis for Hypothesis One

Dependent Variable: WELFARE

Method: Least Squares

Date: 05/18/21 Time: 23:57

Sample: 1 297

Included observations: 297

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	11.67963	0.350348	33.33720	0.0000
ACCESS	0.601600	0.021064	28.56107	0.0000
R	0.898205	Prob(F-statistic)		0.000000
R-squared	0.806273	Mean dependent var		20.85859
Adjusted R-squared	0.805285	S.D. dependent var		4.448259
S.E. of regression	1.962863	Akaike info criterion		4.196734
Sum squared resid	755.1545	Schwarz criterion		4.229949
Log likelihood	-413.4767	Hannan-Quinn criter.		4.210179
F-statistic	815.7345	Durbin-Watson stat		0.036297

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Computation: Eview ver. 7

Table 2 shows the regression analysis result for hypothesis one. Hypothesis one states that access to financial services has no significant effect on the welfare of members of women cooperative societies in Anambra state. The dependent variable in the regression analysis carried out is welfare of members of women cooperative

societies while the independent variable is access to financial services. The result from the analysis as shown in Table 2 is as follows:

$$\text{WELFARE} = 11.67963C + 0.601600\text{ACCESS}$$

The Constant Term (C) obtained is = 11.67963 and it is statistically significant with a p-value of 0.0000 (p-value < 0.05).

The coefficient of ACCESS is 0.601600 and it is statistically significant with a p-value 0.0000 (p-value < 0.05).

The correlation coefficient (r) is 0.898205 signifying that a positive relationship exists between the variables.

The coefficient of determination (R^2) obtained is 0.806273 indicating that approximately, an 81% change in the dependent variable is explained by changes in the independent variables. That is to say, access to financial services has a significant effect on the welfare of members of women cooperative societies in Anambra state.

The F-statistics as shown in the table is 815.7345 and the sig (p-value) obtained as indicated by the Prob(F-statistic) is 0.00000. This indicates that the model is a good fit and that the effect observed is statistically significant (not by chance). This is in accordance to the decision rule which states that if the p-value obtained is less than 0.05, it means that the effect is statistically significant and, therefore, the alternate hypothesis should be accepted. It is then stated that access to financial services has a statistically significant effect on the welfare of members of women cooperative societies in Anambra state.

Decision: Accept the alternate hypothesis.

The findings from the test of hypothesis show that access to financial services has a statistically significant effect on the welfare of members of women cooperative societies in Anambra state.

This is following the result of the analysis carried out using regression analysis which returned a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.806273, indicating that approximately, an 81% change in the dependent variable is explained by changes in the independent variables and a correlation coefficient (r) of 0.898205, indicating a positive relationship between the variables.

These results are statistically significant because the p-value obtained is less than the level of significance used (P-value < 0.5). This result implies that that the more the members of women cooperative societies in Anambra state access finance, the more their welfare is improved. That is, when the women are able to get the finance and support required to carry out their daily activity, support their family and business, the more they would be able to improve their standard of living by buying the necessities of life, like clothes, food, shelter and cater for their family. Their health care would also improve as they would be able to take care of themselves, afford medical care and good

hospital. All these are made possible by access to finance in form of loans, grants and overdrafts where possible.

This result agrees with that of Allen, Demirguc-Kunt, Klapper and Peria (2016) that examined the determinants of financial inclusion and found that nearness to banking services, which is a precursor to access to finance, political stability, low cost of operating accounts and improved legal rights were the key determinants of financial inclusion, which will in turn better the welfare of people. Also, the study aligns with the findings of Abel, Mutandwa and Roux (2018) that investigated the determinants of inclusive finance in Zimbabwe and revealed through their findings that confidence in the financial system, age, education, literacy, income, and access to internet are significant determinants for financial inclusion.

Access to the internet is a huge part of access to finance because without internet, the banks may not function properly and internet banking will be less optimal. Also in line with the findings of the present study is the finding of David, Oluseyi and Emmanuel (2018) that examined the determinants of financial inclusion in Nigeria and indicated that among others, credit to micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) and internet users are significant determinants of financial inclusion in Nigeria. Credit MSMEs will also tantamount to access to finance for members of women cooperative which will improve their welfare and that of their family.

Conclusively, the study reviewed that access to financial services has helped improved the welfare of members of women cooperative societies in Anambra state, Nigeria. Sequel to the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

That the government, in conjunction with various banks, including Central, Commercial and Microfinance banks organize training in the form of workshops and seminars to educate women, especially the rural dwellers on various programmes designed to enhance their access to finance and various things needed to key into such programmes.

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